

D6.12

Quality analysis protocols and quality guidelines

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Deliverable 6.12 Quality analysis protocols and quality guidelines

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.12 reports the protocols and parameters of quality of the obtained oils under the task 6.6 “Evaluation of the olive oil quality from the different management scenarios and study the impact of restoration on the overall quality of the product” during the Diagnostic pre-operational stage of SOIL O-LIVE project. This document describes the protocols for the analysis of the quality parameters set by the International Olive Council (COI or IOC) for the olive oils obtained from the selected orchards.

The sampling protocol follows the same procedure as for pesticide residue analysis in olive oil. A total of 1.1 L of olive oil is required, divided into two 0.5 L glass bottles and one 0.1 L PET bottle. Ideally, olives should be collected entirely from orchards, but if not, random primary samples should be taken to ensure representativeness. Oil extraction should be done promptly using the Abencor® system, or olives should be frozen. Samples must be stored at 4°C, protected from light and heat, and shipped quickly to the UJA laboratory with proper packaging and documentation.

To determine the quality parameters of the produced oils, the samples were subjected to a batch of tests based on the following methods:

- Spectrophotometric investigation in the ultraviolet (COI/T.20/Doc. No 19., Rev. 5 (2019)).
- Determination of the total phenols’ content by spectrophotometric analysis (Folin-Ciocalteu method).
- Determination of fatty acid composition (COI/T.20/Doc. No 33. Rev. 1 (2017)).
- Determination of acidity (COI/T.20/Doc. No 34. Rev. 1 (2017)).
- Determination of peroxide value (COI/T.20/Doc. No 35. Rev. 1 (2017)).
- Determination of tocopherol and tocotrienol contents (ISO 9936:2016).

The information obtained from the relevant analyses of the different oils will be used to assess their quality during the project's pre-operational phase. All oils will be classified based on the parameters established by the COI/IOC.

Table of Acronyms

ρ – is the concentration, in micrograms per millilitre, of α -tocopherol in the standard solution

\bar{A}_s – is the mean of the peak areas obtained for the α -tocopherol standard

\bar{A}_t – is the mean of the peak areas obtained for the α -tocopherol in the test sample

A_i – is the area under the peak of the individual fatty acid methyl ester i ;

c – concentration of the solution in g/100 mL

c – the exact concentration in moles per liter of the titrated solution of potassium hydroxide used

E_λ – extinction (absorbance) measured at wavelength λ

FC - Folin-Ciocalteu

FFA – Free fatty acids

GC-FID – Gas-chromatograph with ion flame ionization detector

GC-MS – Gas-chromatograph with mass spectrometer detector

HPLC – High Pressure Liquid Chromatography

HPLC-FLD – High-pressure liquid chromatograph with fluorescence detector

IOC – International Olive Council

K_m - Specific extinctions

KOH – Potassium hydroxide

K_λ – specific extinction at wavelength λ

M – the mass of the sample, in grams.

M – 282 g/mol, the molar mass in grams per mole of oleic acid

Meq – milliequivalent

Na_2CO_3 – Sodium carbonate

PET – polyethylene terephthalate

PTFE – Polytetrafluoroethylene

s – path length of the quartz cell in cm

T – the exact molarity of the sodium thiosulphate solution used, in mol/L

TAGs – Bound fatty acids of the triacylglycerols

THF – Tetrahydrofuran

V – the number of ml of the standardized sodium thiosulphate solution used for the test, corrected to take into account the blank test

V – the volume of titrated potassium hydroxide solution used, in milliliters

ΔK - Variation in the specific extinction

λ_{em} – Wavelength (emission)

ΣA – is the sum of the areas under all the peaks of all the individual fatty acid methyl esters.

1. Introduction

This document is intended to be used by SOIL O-LIVE partners and, in a simplified version (the sampling protocol), by farmers involved in Tasks 6.5 and 6.6.

The present document includes the sampling protocol for olives and the production of olive oil for laboratory analysis, together with a summary of the standard protocols that will be used for the evaluation of the quality of the produced olive oils in the different cultivars. Most of these protocols are standard methods published by the International Olive Council (IOC) or the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). IOC methods are used for the EU official authorities in the checks of conformity with marketing standards for the olive oils [1,2].

1.1 Material and equipment

Table 1. Material and equipment

Spectrophotometer	
Ultrasonic bath	
Centrifuge	
Plastic syringe	
Quartz cuvette	
Analytical balance	
0.45 µm PVDF filter	
0.45 µm nylon filter	
Volumetric flask (50, 25, 10 mL)	
Conical flask (250 mL)	
Burette (10, 25 mL)	
Cyclohexane (HPLC-grade)	
Heptane (HPLC-grade)	
<i>n</i> -heptane (HPLC-grade)	
Isooctane (HPLC-grade)	
Methanol (HPLC-grade)	
Ultrapure water (HPLC-grade)	
THF (HPLC-grade)	
Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) reagent	
Sodium carbonate (Na ₂ CO ₃) (99 %)	CAS: 497-19-8
Gallic acid (99%)	CAS: 149-91-7
Potassium hydroxide (KOH) (>85 %)	CAS: 1310-58-3
Screw cap test tube (5 mL)	
Diethyl ether	CAS: 60-29-7
Ethanol (95 %)	CAS: 64-17-5
Phenolphthalein	CAS: 77-09-8
Potassium iodide (>99%)	CAS: 7681-11-0
Sodium thiosulfate (99%)	CAS: 7772-98-7
Starch	CAS: 9005-84-9
Chloroform (>99 %)	CAS: 67-66-3
Acetic acid (>99%)	CAS: 64-19-7

α -, β -, γ -, and δ -tocopherols and tocotrienols standard	REF: 613424
Potassium hydroxide titrated ethanolic solution	REF: 1091151000
Gas-chromatograph with ion flame ionization detector (GC-FID)	Column: poly(90% biscyanopropyl/10% cyanopropylphenyl siloxane) phase (60m, 0.25mm, 0.25 μ m). Ref. SP-2380 Sigma-Aldrich.
Gas-chromatograph with mass spectrometer detector (GC-MS)	Column: poly(90% biscyanopropyl/10% cyanopropylphenyl siloxane) phase (60m, 0.25mm, 0.25 μ m). Ref. SP-2380 Sigma-Aldrich.
High-pressure liquid chromatograph with fluorescence detector (HPLC-FLD)	Column: HPLC silica stationary phase (4.6 mm x 250 mm, 5 μ m)

2. Sampling

The sampling protocol described in the present document is the same protocol described for analyzing pesticide residues in olive oil samples (see D6.9). **For all the analysis performed in the WP6 of the project, a total amount of 1.1 L of olive oil is required, separated into three different containers: two glass bottles of 0.5 L of capacity and one plastic bottle of 0.1 L of capacity.** Among plastics, polyethylene terephthalate (PET) satisfying food contact requirements is recommended.

The preferred option for the sampling is the total collection of the olives from the orchards, if possible. If there is no possibility, the sampling procedure applied should ensure that the global sample is representative of the lot. The sample will be a mixture of different portions of olives (primary samples) that should be taken at random at different points and depths from the container in which the olives have been collected [3,4]. For olives which can be assumed to be distributed uniformly inside a lot, it is sufficient to take three primary samples (of 1.5 kg approx.) per lot to form the global sample of around 5 kg [4]. Each global sample should be considered to be homogeneous in terms of analytical characteristics.

Olive oil should be extracted from fresh olives as fast as possible by means of an Abencor® system, following the procedure described in [section 2.1](#). If the extraction of oil cannot be made in the following 48h, the olives should be frozen until extraction. All the olive oil obtained by Abencor® should be mixed for homogenization and divided into three bottles: two amber glass bottles of 0.5 L and one PET bottle (amber color) of 0.1 L of capacity. The bottles should be like the one represented in Fig. 1 or equivalent.

Fig 1. PET/glass amber color bottle for oils. Source: SUNBOX webpage ([link](#))

Sample containers shall be clean and dry prior to use. Sampling shall be carried out in such a manner as to protect the samples from light and heat, avoiding contamination from extraneous material. The containers shall be almost completely filled; the little air space (headspace) shall not be too large, since air has a detrimental action on most fats (nitrogen flow should be applied if possible). Samples shall be protected from light and heat. They should be kept in the fridge (4 °C) and sent as soon as possible to the laboratory of analysis (UJA)ⁱ.

The olive oil farm dispatches the packaged sample (3 bottles of the same olive oil sample) to the laboratory in charge of the analysis of the samples (UJA). **It is very important, especially in the case of glass bottles, to ensure to use a proper packaging to avoid breakage or sample loss**

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during the shipment. Insert in the package a printed document (sampling sheet) with the information of the sample (identification of the orchard, date of olives collection, olives storage conditions -if applicable-, date of olive oil extraction, oil yield %, olive oil storage conditions -if applicable-). This information should be also sent in a digital document (e.g., Word document).

The shipment of the samples to the laboratory has to be carried out in the shortest time possible by tracked expedition and the related cost will be paid by the farm which sends the samples.

*** Note 1:** for the shipment, we suggest specifying in the package description "Olive oil samples for scientific research purposes without any commercial values".

****Note 2:** In case the extraction of olive oil by an Abencor® system is not available on-site, first-extraction virgin olive oil may be obtained in a mill, in similar conditions to those indicated in [section 2.1](#). Malaxation of the olive paste should take place during 30 min and temperature should not exceed 30 °C. If the extraction conditions differ from these ones, they should be indicated in the sampling sheet (annex I). In addition, the same extraction conditions should be used in the campaigns before and after the restoration, in order to obtain results suitable for comparison. Industrial oil yield% should be annotated in the sampling sheet.

The last option, which may be not suitable in due to the shipment costs, is to send to the laboratory a quantity of olives enough to obtain approx. 1 L of olive oil in total by Abencor® system. Considering an industrial oil yield of 20% (a lower value is expected in the selected extraction conditions by Abencor®), 5 kg of frozen olives are required. The olives should be packed in materials chemically inert, if possible, and in a cold environment with dry ice.

2.1 Olive oil production in the Abencor® system

Start by grinding a sample of at least 1 kg of olives in the crusher. Weigh 500 g of the obtained paste into each mixing jar and insert them in the Abencor® thermo-malaxator. It is possible to process simultaneously eight mixing jars. Malaxation will take place during 30 minutes without water addition and under controlled temperature. The bath temperature should be maintained at 30 °C.

If the paste emulsifies when malaxation begins, 1.7% talc may be added. An emulsified olive paste is fluid in texture and has a very uniform appearance, looking like a fruit purée. The oil does not float on the surface during malaxation and the blades are always coated with olive paste [4]. If this occurs and the malaxation take place with processing aids (talc), it should be indicated in the sampling sheet.

After the malaxation, the paste will be centrifuged for 2 min at 3500 rpm in the Abencor® centrifuge to separate the olive oil from solids. Collect the separated liquids (olive oil and water from the olive paste) in a 500-mL graduated glass cylinder and leave them to settle. After phase separation, read the volume of oil and convert it to weight for oil yield calculation [5]. Finally, filter the extracted oils and pack them in three different bottles, as indicated previously.

$$Oil\ yield(\%) = \left(\frac{mL\ olive\ oil \cdot 0.915\ g\ mL^{-1}}{g\ olive\ paste} \right) \cdot 100$$

2.2 Sampling sheet template

When collecting and packing samples, it is important to keep accurate records of the process to ensure proper handling and analysis. To achieve this, all relevant information about the sample collection and packing should be documented and recorded in the table existing in ANNEX 1. This table (sampling sheet) should include details such as the date and time of the sample collection, the location of the collection, and any specific handling or packing instructions. Having this information in a clear and organized format allows for easy reference and ensures that all necessary steps are taken to maintain the integrity and traceability of the sample.

2.3 Reception of samples in the laboratory

At the reception of the samples, the laboratory is responsible for:

- Checking the integrity of the shipped bottles. In case of breakages or leakages, the farmers should be contacted, and a new shipment should be arranged.
- Checking that all the information required in Annex 1 has been filled in by the farmers for each sample. If some information is missing, they should immediately ask the farmers.
- Storing the sample information, protecting the identity of the olive oil farm according to the confidentiality agreement.
- Building an Excel sheet with correct equivalence between the sample name given by the farmer and the unique sample code to be used in the laboratory.

3. Reagents

- Cyclohexane (HPLC-grade)
- Heptane (HPLC-grade)
- Isooctane (HPLC-grade)
- Methanol:water (80:20, v/v)
- Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) reagent
- Na₂CO₃ solution in water (20%, w/v)
- Gallic acid solution
- Methanol KOH solution (2 M)
- Diethyl ether:ethanol solution (1:1, v/v)
- Phenolphthalein, 10 g/l solution in 95 % ethanol (v/v)
- Potassium hydroxide titrated ethanolic solution, c(KOH) (0.1 M)
- Potassium iodide, saturated aqueous solution
- Sodium thiosulfate solution in ultrapure water (0.01 M)
- Starch solution in ultrapure water (10 g/L)

- Chloroform
- Acetic acid
- Standard solution of tocols in n-heptane (10 mg in 50 mL of n-heptane for each standard)
- THF:heptane (3.8 : 96.2 %, v/v)

4. Spectrophotometric investigation in the ultraviolet

Spectrophotometric examination in the ultraviolet can provide information on the quality of a fat, its state of preservation and changes brought about by technological processes. The protocol for the determination of phenolic compounds in olive oils will be the IOC method described in the document COI/T.20/Doc. No 19., Rev. 5 (2019) [6].

The absorption at the wavelengths specified in the method is due to the presence of conjugated diene and triene systems resulting from oxidation processes and/or refining practices. These absorptions are expressed as specific extinctions or extinction coefficients, conventionally indicated by *K*. These coefficients indicate the extinction of 1% (m/V) solution of the fat in the specified solvent, in a 10 mm cell.

The specific extinctions at 232 nm and 268 nm in isooctane or 232 nm and 270 nm in cyclohexane are calculated for a concentration of 1% (m/V) in a 10 mm cell (quartz cuvette). K_{232} is indicative of the initial oxidation of the oil, and the absorption at this wavelength is attributed to the presence of hydroperoxides and conjugated dienes. On the other hand, K_{270} (K_{268} in isooctane) is used to detect the presence of secondary oxidation products (aldehydes, ketones, etc.) and/or the presence of compounds that are formed in the refining of the oils. High values of K_{232} and K_{270} are synonymous with poor quality oils [7].

Delta K: After measuring the absorbance at 268 or 270 nm (λ_{max}), measure the absorbance at λ_{max} , λ_{max+4} and λ_{max-4} . These absorbance values are used to determine the variation in the specific extinction (ΔK). This test is used to detect if refined oil has been mixed with virgin olive oils [7].

4.1 Sample preparation

Dilution 1% (w/v): weigh accurately approximately 0.25 g (± 1 mg) of the olive oil sample and dissolve it in cyclohexane using a volumetric flask of 25 mL. Homogenize. Filter quickly through paper if the solution is not clear.

Prepare a second dilution of 0.05 g of virgin olive oil in 25 mL of cyclohexane for measurements at 232 nm.

4.2 Absorbance measurements

Measurements will be done in rectangular quartz cuvettes having an optical path-length of 10 mm. A spectrophotometer suitable for measurements at ultraviolet wavelengths having nominal spectral bandwidths of 5 nm or less will be used.

Fill the quartz cuvette with the test solution and measure the extinctions at 232, and 270 nm (or 268 nm in isooctane) against the solvent used as a reference. The extinction values recorded must lie within the range 0.1 to 0.8 or within the range of linearity of the spectrophotometer.

4.3 Expression of results

Specific extinctions (K): expressed to two decimal places, are calculated as follows:

$$K_{\lambda} = \frac{E_{\lambda}}{c \cdot s}$$

Where:

K_{λ} : specific extinction at wavelength λ

E_{λ} : extinction (absorbance) measured at wavelength λ

c : concentration of the solution in g/100 mL

s : path length of the quartz cell in cm

Variation of the specific extinction (ΔK), expressed to two decimal places, is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta K = K_m - \left(\frac{K_{m-4} + K_{m+4}}{2} \right)$$

Where:

K_m : is the specific extinction at the wavelength for maximum absorption at 270 nm or 268 nm, depending on the solvent used.

5. Determination of the total phenols' content by spectrophotometric analysis

The protocol for the extraction of phenolic compounds in olive oils will be the IOC method number 1, described in the document COI/T.20/Doc. No 29. Rev. 2 (2022) [8], with small modifications. The spectrophotometric analysis will follow the Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) assay [9], with small modifications [10].

5.1 Extraction of Phenolic compounds

Briefly, the procedure is as follows:

1. In a 10 mL screw-cap glass test tube, accurately weigh 2.0 g of olive oil.
2. Seal with the screw cap and shake for exactly 30 s.
3. Add 5 mL of the methanol/water 80/20 (% v/v) extraction solution.
4. Shake for exactly 1 min.
5. Extract in the ultrasonic bath for 15 min at room temperature.
6. Centrifuge at 5000 rpm for 25 min.
7. Take an aliquot of the supernatant phase and, in case of turbidity, filter through a 5 mL plastic syringe, with a 0.45 µm PVDF filter.

5.2 Folin – Ciocalteu (FC) assay

1. Add 0.5 mL of FC reagent to a 10 mL volumetric flask containing approx. 1mL of distilled water.
2. Add 0.2 mL of the phenolic extract, obtained as detailed before, and mix.
3. Add 1.5 mL of aqueous Na₂CO₃ (20%, w/v), reaching the final volume with distilled water.
4. Store each flask for a period of 2 h at room temperature in dark.
5. Measure the absorbance at 760 nm in a 1-cm cuvette.

Total phenols are quantified using a calibration curve built using gallic acid aqueous solutions at different concentrations (2 – 10 mg/L). Also, it is important to prepare and read a proper blank (methanol:water (80:20, v/v) to subtract its absorbance from that of the samples.

The blank and gallic acid standard solutions follow the FC colorimetric assay procedure described for the samples and simultaneously to them.

Results are expressed as $\frac{mg \text{ gallic acid}}{kg \text{ of oil}}$.

6. Determination of fatty acid composition

The protocol for the determination of the fatty acid composition in olive oils will be the IOC method described in the document COI/T.20/Doc. No 33. Rev. 1 (2017) [11]. The bound fatty acids of the triacylglycerols (TAGs) of vegetable fats and oils and, depending on the esterification method, the free fatty acids (FFA), are converted into fatty acid methyl esters (FAME), which are determined by capillary gas chromatography.

6.1 Sample preparation

Methyl esters are formed by trans-esterification with methanolic potassium hydroxide as an intermediate stage before saponification takes place. The procedure is as follows:

1. In a 5 mL screw-top test tube weigh approximately 0.1 g of the oil sample.
2. Add 2 mL of hexane, and shake.
3. Add 0.2 mL of the methanolic potassium hydroxide solution (2 mol/L), put on the cap of the tube fitted with a PTFE joint, tighten the cap, and shake vigorously for 30 seconds.
4. Leave to stratify until the upper solution becomes clear.
5. Decant the upper layer containing the methyl esters and transfer to a vial. The heptane solution is ready for injection into the gas chromatograph.

Note. - It is advisable to keep the solution in the refrigerator until gas chromatographic analysis. Storage of the solution for more than 12 hours is not recommended.

6.2 Analysis of fatty acid methyl esters by gas chromatography

A gas chromatograph with flame ionization detector (FID) will be used. The separation of the FAMES will take place in a polar capillary column.

Column: poly(90% biscyanopropyl/10% cyanopropylphenyl siloxane) phase (60m, 0.25mm, 0.25µm). Ref. SP-2380 Sigma-Aldrich.

Chromatographic and detector conditions:

- Inlet temperature: 250 °C
- Split ratio: 1:100
- Carrier gas: Helium (1.5 mL/min)
- Injection volume: 1 µl
- Detector temperature: 250 °C
- Oven gradient:

Table 2. Oven gradient

Rate °C/min	Temperature °C	Hold time min
-	165	8
2	210	1

Total analysis time: 31.5 min

The column will be conditioned according to the instructions of the vendor, previously to the analysis of the olive oil samples.

6.3 Expression of results

The chromatographic peaks will be tentatively identified by GC-FID based on their elution order, according to the standard COI/T.20/Doc. No 33. Rev. 1 (2017) [11]. Confirmation by GC-MS may be possible if needed.

The mass fraction W_i (%component “i”) of the individual fatty acid methyl esters, expressed as a percentage by mass of methyl esters, will be calculated as follows:

$$W_i = \frac{A_i}{\sum A} \cdot 100$$

where:

A_i : is the area under the peak of the individual fatty acid methyl ester i ;

$\sum A$: is the sum of the areas under all the peaks of all the individual fatty acid methyl esters.

7. Determination of acidity

The protocol for the determination of the fatty acid composition in olive oils will be the IOC method described in the document COI/T.20/Doc. No 34. Rev. 1 (2017) [12]. This method describes the determination of free fatty acids in olive oils and olive pomace oils. A sample is dissolved in a mixture of solvents and the free fatty acids present are titrated using a potassium hydroxide or sodium hydroxide solution. The content of free fatty acids is expressed as acidity, calculated as the percentage of oleic acid.

7.1 Reagents

- Diethyl ether; 95 % ethanol (v/v), mixture of equal parts by volume.
- *Neutralize precisely at the moment of use with the potassium hydroxide solution, with the addition of 0.3 ml of the phenolphthalein solution per 100 mL of mixture.*
- Potassium hydroxide titrated ethanolic solution, c(KOH) about 0.1 mol/L or, if necessary, c(KOH) about 0.5 mol/L. Commercial solutions are available.
- Phenolphthalein, 10 g/L solution in 95 to 96 % ethanol (v/v).
- Alternative for strongly coloured oils: alkali blue 6B or thymolphthalein, 20 g/L solution in 95 to 96 % ethanol (v/v).

7.2 Procedure

When the sample is cloudy, it should be filtered.

1. Weigh 10 ± 0.02 g of olive oil sample (expected acidity ≤ 2 g oleic acid/ 100 g) in a 250 mL conical flask (Erlenmeyer flask).
2. Dissolve the sample in 50 to 100 mL of the previously neutralized mixture of diethyl ether and ethanol.
3. Using a 10 ml burette (class A, graduated in 0.05 mL), titrate while stirring with the 0.1 mol/L solution of potassium hydroxide until the indicator changes (the color of the colored indicator persists for at least 10 seconds).

Note 1.- If the quantity of 0.1 mol/L potassium hydroxide solution required exceeds 10 mL, use the 0.5 mol/L solution, or change the sample mass according to the instruction given in the standard COI/T.20/Doc. No 34. Rev. 1 (2017) [12].

Note 2.- If the solution becomes cloudy during titration, add enough of the solvents to give a clear solution.

Carry out a second determination only if the first result is higher than the specified limit for the category of the oil.

7.3 Expression of results

Acidity, as percentage of oleic acid by weight is equal to:

$$V \cdot c \cdot \frac{M}{1000} \cdot \frac{100}{m} = \frac{V \cdot c \cdot M}{10 \cdot m}$$

where:

V: the volume of titrated potassium hydroxide solution used, in milliliters

c: the exact concentration in moles per liter of the titrated solution of potassium hydroxide used

M: 282 g/mol, the molar mass in grams per mole of oleic acid

m: the mass of the sample, in grams.

Oleic acidity is reported as follows:

(a) to two decimal places for values from 0 up to and including 1

(b) to one decimal place for values from 1 up to and including 100

8. Determination of peroxide value

The protocol for the determination of the peroxide value in olive oils will be the IOC method described in the document COI/T.20/Doc. No 35. Rev. 1 (2017) [13]. The peroxide value is the quantity of those substances in the sample, expressed in terms of milliequivalents of active oxygen per kilogram, which oxidize potassium iodide under the operating conditions described in the standard.

The method is based on the treatment of the test portion, in solution in acetic acid and chloroform, by a solution of potassium iodide. Titration of the liberated iodine with standardized sodium thiosulfate solution.

8.1 Reagents

- Potassium iodide, saturated aqueous solution, recently prepared, free from iodine and iodates. Dissolve approximately 14 g of potassium iodide in approximately 10 mL of water at room temperature.
- Sodium thiosulfate, 0.01 mol/L (equivalent to 0.01 N) accurately standardized aqueous solution, standardized just before use.
- Starch solution, 10 g/L aqueous dispersion, recently prepared from natural soluble starch.

8.2 Procedure

The test shall be carried out in diffuse daylight or in artificial light.

1. Prepare 250 mL conical flasks, with ground necks and stoppers, dried beforehand and filled with a pure, dry inert gas (nitrogen or, preferably, carbon dioxide)
2. Weigh in a glass scoop or, failing this, in a flask, to the nearest 0.001 g, a mass of the sample in accordance with the following table, according to the expected peroxide value:

Table 3. Expected peroxide value and sample weight

Expected peroxide value (meqO ₂ /kg)	Weight of test portion (g)
0 to 12	5.0 to 2.0
12 to 20	2.0 to 1.2
20 to 30	1.2 to 0.8
30 to 50	0.8 to 0.5
50 to 90	0.5 to 0.3

3. Unstop a flask and introduce the glass scoop containing the test portion. Add 10 mL of chloroform and dissolve the test portion rapidly by stirring.

4. Add 15 mL of acetic acid, then 1 mL of potassium iodide solution.
5. Insert the stopper quickly, shake for one minute, and leave for exactly five minutes away from the light at a temperature from 15 to 25 °C.
6. Add about 75 mL of ultrapure water.
7. Using a burette of 25 mL, titrate the liberated iodine with the sodium thiosulphate solution shaking vigorously, using starch solution as indicator.
8. Carry out two determinations on the same test sample.

Carry out simultaneously a blank test. If the result of the blank exceeds 0.05 mL of the 0.01 N Sodium thiosulfate solution, replace the impure reagents.

8.3 Expression of results

The peroxide value (PV), expressed in milliequivalents of active oxygen per kilogram, is given by the formula:

$$PV = \frac{V \cdot T \cdot 1000}{m}$$

Where:

V: the number of ml of the standardized sodium thiosulphate solution used for the test, corrected to take into account the blank test

T: the exact molarity of the sodium thiosulphate solution used, in mol/L

M: the weight in g, of the test portion

Take as the result the arithmetic mean of the two determinations carried out.

Report the result of the determination to one decimal place.

9. Determination of tocopherol and tocotrienol contents

The protocol for the determination of tocopherol and tocotrienol contents in olive oils will be the method described in the standard ISO 9936:2016 [14]. This International Standard specifies a method for the determination of the contents of free α -, β -, γ -, and δ -tocopherols and tocotrienols (referred to jointly as tocols) in animal and vegetable fats and oils by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).

9.1 Sample preparation

Olive oil samples are dissolved in *n*-heptane. A solution of 10 mg/mL is prepared, although appropriate dilutions of the test sample may be needed, depending on the concentration of tocols. The test solution is prepared as follows:

1. Weigh, to the nearest 1 mg, 0,25 g \pm 0,1 g of the olive oil sample (test sample) into a 25 ml one-mark volumetric flask.
2. Add a quantity of *n*-heptane, swirling to dissolve the test portion, and dilute to the mark with the same solvent.
3. Filter the solution with an HPLC nylon filter 0,45 μ m if not clear.

9.2 Standard solution of tocols

Working standard solutions of tocols are also prepared in *n*-heptane. A standard solution containing a mixture of the tocols is prepared according to the sensitivity of the fluorescence detector used. For example, a concentration in the range 1 – 5 μ g/mL may be used.

Sample and standard solutions are freshly prepared prior to the analysis and protected from light.

9.3 Determination of tocols by HPLC

Separations are carried out at room temperature (20 ± 2 °C) in a chromatographic column packed with silica stationary phase (4.6 mm x 250 mm, 5 μ m). Injection volume of samples and standards is 10 μ L or 20 μ L according to detector sensitivity.

The mobile phase is a mixture of THF:heptane 3.8:96.2 (v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min (isocratic mode). Chromatographic peaks are recorded by fluorescence detector at λ_{ex} 296 nm and λ_{em} 330 nm.

9.4 Expression of results

The α -tocopherol content, w , of the sample, expressed in milligrams per kilogram (mg/kg), is given by the formula:

$$w = \frac{\rho \cdot \bar{A}_t \cdot V}{\bar{A}_s \cdot m}$$

where

ρ : is the concentration, in micrograms per millilitre, of α -tocopherol in the standard solution

\bar{A}_s : is the mean of the peak areas obtained for the α -tocopherol standard

\bar{A}_t : is the mean of the peak areas obtained for the α -tocopherol in the test sample

m : is the mass, in grams, of the test sample

V : is the volume of test solution prepared (= 25 mL)

If the chromatographic peaks of the remaining tocopherols are relevant, calculate their respective contents of the test sample in the same way, using the data obtained from the corresponding standard.

If the only standard available is α -tocopherol, relate all tocopherols to this standard, but make this clear when reporting the results.

10. References

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ANNEX 1: Sampling sheet template.

Sample name Reference code	Patch Id	Date of olives collection	Date of oil extraction	Oil yield (%)*	Storage conditions oil	Storage conditions olives	Additional information
Sample name Code XXXX							

*Oil yield (%) = (kg of oil obtained/kg of olives crushed) x100

ANNEX 2: Report template

Report XXXXXX/20XX

No of pages: XXXX

Reception date:

Starting date:

Finishing date:

Report elaborated by:

Test

Quality Analysis protocols of olive oil

Samples

1. Sample name
 - a. Sample code

Test Method

Quality Analysis protocols of olive oil

Results

Quality Analysis protocols of olive oil

Starting date: XX/XX/XXXX

Finishing date: XX/XX/XXXX

Table 1. Results of spectrophotometric test, acidity, peroxide value and α -tocopherol

Sample	Test results						
	Absorbancy in UV			FC assay ($\frac{mg \text{ gallic acid}}{kg \text{ of oil.}}$)	Acidity (Oleic acidity %)	PV (meqO ₂ /kg)	α -tocopherol (mg/kg)
	K ₂₃₂	K ₂₇₀	ΔK				
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>							
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>							
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>							
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>							
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>							
Sample name <i>Code XXXX</i>							

Table 2. Results of fatty acid composition

Sample	%FAME												
	C14:0	C16:0	C16:1	C17:0	C17:1	C18:0	C18:1	C18:2	C18:3	C20:0	C20:1	C22:0	C24:0
Sample name													
Code XXXX													
Sample name													
Code XXXX													
Sample name													
Code XXXX													
Sample name													
Code XXXX													
Sample name													
Code XXXX													

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